

How to Write a Data Management Plan (DMP)?

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This guideline explains how to create, maintain, and publish a Data Management Plan (DMP). It covers funder requirements, templates, tools, collaboration, version control, and publication options.

Background and Aim

A DMP is a formal and living document that defines responsibilities and provides guidance. It describes the research data itself along with all steps of the data life cycle necessary for effective management during the project phase as well as prescribed measures for publishing and archiving after the project has ended [Lindstädt *et al.* 2019; Vandendorpe and Lindstädt 2020; Cozatl *et al.* 2021; Assmann *et al.* 2022, March]. Ideally, a DMP saves time and effort for yourself and others by planning ahead [Bobrov *et al.* 2021; Assmann *et al.* 2022, March] and ensuring that data become Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). A DMP can also facilitate and harmonise the coordination and shared use of data by multiple project partners, as well as improve knowledge management (even when staff changes) [modified from Di Donato 2021 slide 36 and Tonello 2021; Assmann *et al.* 2022, March].

The following steps outline how to start writing a DMP and keep it up to date.

Guideline Steps

Step 1: Start Early

A DMP is ideally set up before the project starts or at the start of the project (see Step 2 for specific requirements of funders) [Rathmann *et al.* 2021, Voigt *et al.* 2022]. However, it is never too late to create a DMP for ongoing projects missing a formal plan.

Step 2: Determine the Funder Requirements

Funders have different requirements for the creation, updating and content of DMPs. Be sure to check these requirements before you start writing your DMP.

In Europe, **Horizon Europe** requires a DMP to be submitted within the first six months of a funded project [Steen *et al.* 2022]. This DMP must be written using the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#) and updated regularly [Bres *et al.* 2023] throughout the project [Vieten *et al.* 2023].

In Germany, the **German Research Foundation (DFG)** does not require a formal DMP, but information on the handling of research data must be provided [Bres *et al.* 2023]. This information must be submitted with the proposal. The DFG [checklist for handling research data](#) can be used to ensure that important issues are covered. It is not necessary to update the DMP [Bres *et al.* 2023] during the project [Vieten *et al.* 2023]. The **German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)** requires a formal DMP depending on the grant/programme. If required, the DMP must be submitted with the application. The content and required updates also depend on the grant/programme [Bres *et al.* 2023]. The **Volkswagen Foundation** requires a DMP to be submitted with the proposal. The [basic DMP template](#) provided by the foundation can be used and no updates are required [Bres *et al.* 2023, Vieten *et al.* 2023].

Funder requirements may change over time. Always consult the most recent guidance provided by the funding organisation.

Step 3: Find a Template

There are common elements, general templates and best practices for creating a DMP. There are also specific requirements, components and formats that may vary depending on the purpose or benefit being sought by the user, the funder (see Step 2) or the institution [Vieten *et al.* 2023].

Typically, DMP templates take the form of a questionnaire covering the following topics:

- Project-specific administrative information
- Roles, responsibilities and obligations
- Budget, costs and resources (see [What will it cost to manage and share my data?](#))
- Description of the data to be collected and shared
- Data documentation
- Data access and publication
- Other issues (e.g. FAIR data principles, data quality control, data preparation)

General templates are good for an entire project. Here are two examples of general DMP templates:

- Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN): [webpage](#)
- Science Europe: [download as docx](#)

There are also **discipline-specific templates**, such as:

- **Advanced research computing:** Portage Network ([webpage](#))
- **Agrosystems:** FAIRagro template in [RDMO](#)
- **Chemistry:** NFDI4Chem template ([webpage](#))
- **Educational research:** KonsortSWD template ([webpage](#))
- **Engineering sciences:** NFDI4Ing template in [RDMO](#)
- **Health sciences:**
 - National Institute of Dental and Craniofacial Research ([download as docx](#))
 - NFDI4Health templates ([webpage](#))
 - Portage Network ([webpage](#))
- **Language and text-based research:** Text+ template ([webpage](#))
- **Material and immaterial cultural heritage:** NFDI4Culture template in [RDMO](#)
- **Microbiota research:** NFDI4Microbiota template ([webpage](#))
- **Molecular interactions:** Portage Network ([webpage](#))
- **Plant research:** DataPLANT template ([webpage](#))

Examples of **already completed DMPs** can also be found published online. Two omics-related examples are:

- DD-DeCaF Bioinformatics Services for Data-Driven Design of Cell Factories and Communities: [webpage](#)
- METASTAVA: [webpage](#)

Further DMP templates and examples of completed DMPs can be found in these **DMP catalogues** [Cordes *et al.* 2022; Assmann *et al.* 2022, March]:

- [DMP Catalogue](#) from the LIBER Research Data Management Working Group
- [DMP Templates](#) from the Digital Research Alliance of Canada
- [DMPs](#) in PHAIDRA
- [DMPs](#) in Research Ideas and Outcomes
- [DMPs](#) in Zenodo
- [Example DMPs](#) from the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)
- [Good and bad examples from DMPs](#) (p 10)
- [Public plans](#) from the DMPTool

If you are dealing with research software, you can write a Software Management Plan (SMP) following the questions suggested by [Baxter et al.](#) Projects in which software is a major research output should consider maintaining both a DMP and a SMP.

You can also make your DMP machine-actionable (i.e. structured and machine-readable, allowing for dynamic reporting on the outcomes of a research project, and enabling streamlined information exchange between relevant systems [Praetzellis 2024]) by following the ten principles proposed by [Miksa et al. 2019](#).

Step 4: Involve Your Project Partners, RDM Staff and Central Infrastructure

When you start writing your DMP, you should consult your project partners and your institution's local Research Data Management (RDM) staff. For German institutions, you can check here to find your institution's [research data policy](#) and request [local support](#). You should also consult central infrastructure services, such as the computing centre and library [Assmann et al. 2022, March].

Step 5: Choose a DMP Tool

You may choose to write your DMP in a text editor, but if you are working with several project partners, it may be a good idea to use a DMP tool. There are many different tools available for writing a DMP; they all offer the same benefits/functions, they differ mainly in the funders they specialise in [Bres et al. 2023]. Examples of DMP tools are:

- The open-source [ARGOS](#) developed by OpenAIRE, which can be used to create machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) [Jacob et al. 2022, Cordes et al. 2022, Assmann et al. 2022, August].
- [DataPLAN](#) developed by the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortium DataPLANT for plant research.
- The open-source [DMPonline](#) developed by the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) [Vandendorpe and Lindstädt 2020].
- [GFBio DMPT](#) for biodiversity and environmental research [Jacob et al. 2022].
- The open-source Research Data Management Organiser ([RDMO](#)) funded by the DFG and featuring a plugin architecture that allows the implementation of maDMPs.

An overview of (almost) all DMP tools on the market [Cordes et al. 2022] can be found in the [DMP-Toolguide](#) (only in German) [Helbig et al. 2021].

Step 6: Answer the Questions & Be Realistic

Most DMP templates take the form of a catalogue of questions to be answered. For this step, it is a good idea to get your project collaborators and support staff together to answer the questions.

In any DMP, there may be some questions that are not relevant to your project. Even discipline-specific DMP templates are designed to cover all possible questions and may contain irrelevant questions. Do not worry, not every question needs to be answered. If in doubt, ask your local support or RDM staff [Vieten *et al.* 2023].

The length of a DMP can vary from a few paragraphs to several pages [Assmann *et al.* 2022, March] (about 2 to 15 pages) [Cordes *et al.* 2022]. Be realistic: provide as much information as possible and as much detail as necessary [Assmann *et al.* 2022, November]. At the beginning of the research project (e.g. when you have to submit your DMP together with the proposal), the DMP is quite short and provides basic information. As the project progresses, the DMP contains more and more information, the answers become more detailed and the functions of the DMP increase until it becomes a project management tool [Vieten *et al.* 2023].

Step 7: Review and Revise the DMP Regularly

A good DMP is for the use of all project stakeholders, is well structured and distinguishes between actions to be taken during and after the project. It is a living document that should be regularly edited and updated to reflect the current situation if significant changes in data management occur during the research project [Lindstädt *et al.* 2019, Assmann *et al.* 2022, March, Voigt *et al.* 2022, Vieten *et al.* 2023]. It should be started as early as possible, be as concise as possible, as long as necessary, and contain sufficient detail without being redundant. Ideally, the DMP will be published with the research data at the end of the project [Cordes *et al.* 2022].

Updates to a DMP should reflect any changes in roles, responsibilities and obligations, such as updates to the personnel involved in data management or their specific responsibilities. Revisions may also be necessary when there are changes in data collection, including the introduction of new data types, formats and methods of collection, or changes in data volumes. Modifications to data organisation (e.g. updates to naming conventions) should also be documented. Additionally, updates may be required for data documentation, including changes to metadata standards or the implementation of new procedures for recording data provenance. Data security and storage practices must be revised if there are new security measures or protocols (e.g. encryption), or if the storage infrastructure changes (e.g. adoption of cloud services). In terms of digital preservation, the DMP should be updated to include new archiving strategies or tools. Changes in data access and publishing, such as shifts in licensing (whether data becomes restricted or open access) and the selection of new repositories for data publication, also necessitate revisions. Finally, updates may be driven by ethical considerations, including new legal or regulatory obligations (e.g. if there are changes to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)).

To keep track of versions of a DMP, it is important to implement version control. This includes maintaining a clear version history with timestamps and using [semantic versioning](#) to reflect the significance of changes. For collaborative projects, a version control system such as Git or a dedicated DMP tool such as RDMO can be used to manage revisions efficiently. It is also good practice to maintain a version control table, typically placed at the beginning or end of the DMP, which documents each version along with dates, authors and a summary of changes:

Version	Date	Author	Summary of Changes
v1.0	2025-01-10	Jane Doe	Initial DMP submitted to funder
v1.1	2025-03-22	John Doe	Updated storage and data access and publishing sections

Previous versions should be archived systematically by keeping copies of all past versions and using a consistent file-naming convention. When formally submitting the DMP to a repository such as Zenodo, assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) helps ensure traceability and formal referencing of specific versions.

Step 8: Publish Your DMP

Publishing a DMP increases transparency, supports reproducibility, documents data stewardship practices, and may help other researchers develop their own plans.

If you wish, you can assign a Data Management Plan ID (DMP-ID) to your DMP, which is essentially a DOI with resourceTypeGeneral set to "OutputsManagementPlan".

For example, if you publish your DMP on Zenodo, you can also assign a DOI to it and the resource type "Publication / Output Management Plan". You can also choose to make it open, restricted or embargoed. See examples of DMPs published on Zenodo [here](#).

Contact Persons and Further Information

DMP Experts

- DMP experts at ZB MED: Marisabel Gonzalez-Ocanto (ocanto@zbmed.de)
- DMP expert in NFDI4Microbiota: Clemens Thölken (thoelken@uni-marburg.de)

Further Information

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Further comments

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